

COVID^X

See how we lived the #BackToAHealthyFuture event

#BackToAHealthyFuture turned out to be the event that emphasized the importance of the use of technology within the healthcare sector.

On the 21st and 22nd of September, thanks to COVID-X Program and Inno4cov-19, start-ups, investors, policymakers, big companies and healthcare providers met to enjoy discussions, networking sessions and exhibiting booths where they could discover new solutions in the health and data sector.

COVID-X programme is about to end, but we are very proud of our game changers and the project's results!

[See how it went](#)

Watch the series of game changers' interviews at the #BackToAHealthyFuture event

Irina Kalderon Libal, COVID-X Policy Officer, at #BackToAHealthyFuture event

Watch the
videos

Watch the
video

The latest COVID-X Press Release is out!

The project finishes at the end of this month. Check the results of the COVID-X programme.

ODIN Open Call
**420,000€ available for AI
and Big Data solutions**
Join us!

→ **#ODINopencall**

The ODIN Open Call is open until October 27th at 17:00 CET

ODIN's Open Call→Are you an startup, SME, midcap, industry, research centre or technology organization? Get involved in the #ODINopencall, they are looking for entities leading AI, BigData, DataAnalytics in healthcare to join them!

Open Call

COVID-X

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